

Mercury seen from Mars (local Extrema of apparent brightness from 1984-1991)

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round the Mars.

Explanations: mag = stellar magnitude, °=degree, ' = angular minute, " = angular second

AE= astronomical unit =149598500 km

Date	apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance of Mercury from Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	apparent diameter ["]	Distance of Mercury to Sun [AE]
15.1.1984	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.27-1.28 decreasing	1.21-1.22 increasing	5.2-5.3 increasing	0.38-0.39 increasing
19.3.-22.3.1984	-0.72	93-98 decreasing	1.86-1.91 decreasing	3.32-5.44 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
25.4.1984	weaker than +10.50	<1	1.12	0.17	6.0	0.45
20.6.-21.6.1984	-0.94	99-100 decreasing	1.80-1.81 decreasing	0.37-1.23 increasing	3.7	0.31
12.8.1984	weaker than +7.50	<1	0.98	1.94-1.95 decreasing	6.8	0.46
19.9.-20.9.1984	-0.99	95-98 increasing	1.67-1.69 increasing	4.14-5.57 decreasing	3.9-4.0 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
27.11.1984	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.02	1.60-1.61 decreasing	6.6	0.37
20.12-23.12.1984	-0.73	79-88 increasing	1.56-1.63 increasing	9.16-10.71 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
7.3.1985	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.16	0.02	5.8	0.31
26.3.-28.3.1985	-0.19	69-77 increasing	1.59-1.67 increasing	12.24-12.83 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.36-0.38 increasing
22.4.-30.4.1985	+0.19	99-100 decreasing	1.99-2.00 decreasing	0.75-3.43 increasing	3.3-3.4 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
20.5.-21.5.1985	-0.04	73-77 decreasing	1.70-1.74 decreasing	12.01-12.33 increasing	3.8-4.0 increasing	0.37-0.39 decreasing
10.6.-11.6.1985	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.28	0.96-0.97 increasing	5.2	0.31
5.7.-9.7.1985	+0.36	71-80 increasing	1.75-1.85 increasing	12.90-14.01 decreasing	3.6-3.8 decreasing	0.43-0.45 increasing
10.7.-19.7.1985	+0.37	80-91 increasing	1.85-1.98 increasing	9.75-12.90 decreasing	3.4-3.7 decreasing	0.45-0.47 increasing
21.8.-24.8.1985	-0.27	78-86 decreasing	1.81-1.89 decreasing	8.48-9.66 increasing	3.5-3.7 increasing	0.33-0.36 decreasing
14.9.1985	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.32	1.32-1.33 increasing	5.1	0.34-0.35 increasing
22.11.-24.11.1985	-0.52	88-93 decreasing	1.88-1.93 decreasing	6.01-7.16 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
21.12.1985	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.25-1.26 decreasing	1.11-1.12 increasing	5.3-5.4 increasing	0.39-0.40 increasing
22.2.-24.2.1986	-0.77	95-99 decreasing	1.86-1.89 decreasing	3.01-4.51 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
2.4.-3.4.1986	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.08-1.09 decreasing	0.21	6.2	0.45-0.46 increasing
24.5.-27.5.1986	-0.96	99-100 increasing	1.77-1.78 decreasing	1.26-1.63 decreasing	3.8	0.30-0.31 increasing
21.7.1986	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97-0.98 increasing	2.16-2.18 decreasing	6.9	0.44-0.45 decreasing
25.8.-26.8.1986	-0.97	93-96 increasing	1.65-1.67 increasing	5.54-6.44 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
4.11.1986	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.04	1.27-1.28 decreasing	6.5	0.35
26.11.-27.11.	-0.65	79-83	1.57-1.61	10.42-10.55	4.1-4.3	0.33-0.34

1986		increasing	increasing	decreasing	decreasing	increasing
3.1.-9.1.1987	+0.16	82-90 decreasing	1.70-1.79 decreasing	11.30-13.82 decreasing	3.7-4.0 increasing	0.45-0.47 decreasing
10.1.-18.1.1987	+0.15	67-82 decreasing	1.55-1.70 decreasing	13.82-15.65 increasing	4.0-4.3 increasing	0.42-0.45 decreasing
10.2.1987	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.18	0.26	5.7	0.31
1.3.-5.3.1987	-0.07	66-77 increasing	1.60-1.70 increasing	12.43-13.19 decreasing	3.9-4.2 decreasing	0.36-0.39 increasing
28.3.-31.3.1987	+0.22	99-100 increasing	2.01-2.03 increasing	0.76-7.06 decreasing	3.3	0.47
24.4.-27.4.1987	-0.08	72-80 decreasing	1.71-1.79 decreasing	11.08-11.85 increasing	3.7-3.9 increasing	0.36-0.39 decreasing
17.5.1987	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.29-1.30 decreasing	1.07-1.08 increasing	5.1-5.2 increasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
28.7.-29.7.1987	-0.32	81-87 decreasing	1.84-1.89 decreasing	8.21-9.01 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.33-0.35 decreasing
20.8.-21.8.1987	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.31-1.32 decreasing	1.33-1.35 increasing	5.0-5.1 increasing	0.35
28.10.-29.10.1987	-0.57	90-93 decreasing	1.89-1.92 decreasing	5.69-6.52 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
27.11.1987	weaker than +8.50	<1	1.23	0.97-0.98 increasing	5.4	0.40-0.41 increasing
27.1.-30.1.1988	-0.81	96-100 decreasing	1.84-1.88 decreasing	1.89-4.30 increasing	3.6	0.30-0.32 decreasing
10.3.1988	weaker than +10.50	<1	1.05	0.63-0.64 increasing	6.4	0.46
28.4.-30.4.1988	-0.98	98-100 increasing	1.75-1.76 increasing	0.66-2.62 decreasing	3.8	0.30-0.31 increasing
28.6.1988	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97-0.98 increasing	2.22-2.24 decreasing	6.8-6.9 decreasing	0.42-0.43 decreasing
28.7.-31.7.1988	-0.93	89-95 increasing	1.61-1.66 increasing	6.02-8.10 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
10.10.1988	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.06-1.07 increasing	0.94-0.95 decreasing	6.2-6.3 decreasing	0.34-0.35 decreasing
30.10.-1.11.1988	-0.55	75-82 increasing	1.56-1.62 increasing	10.78-11.60 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.35 increasing
7.12.-10.12.1988	+0.16	90-94 decreasing	1.82-1.86 decreasing	9.00-10.52 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
19.12.-25.12.1988	+0.11	67-79 decreasing	1.57-1.69 decreasing	13.84-14.88 increasing	4.0-4.3 increasing	0.40-0.44 decreasing
15.1.1989	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.21	0.46-0.47 decreasing	5.5	0.31
4.2.-7.2.1989	+0.04	67-76 increasing	1.63-1.72 increasing	12.84-13.44 decreasing	3.9-4.1 decreasing	0.38-0.40 increasing
25.2.-5.3.1989	+0.24	97-100 increasing	1.99-2.04 increasing	1.77-5.63 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
30.3.-31.3.1989	-0.13	76-79 decreasing	1.76-1.79 decreasing	10.78-11.03 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.36-0.37 decreasing
21.4.1989	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31	1.15-1.16 increasing	5.1	0.32
1.7.-4.7.1989	-0.36	81-90 decreasing	1.84-1.92 decreasing	7.29-8.85 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.35 decreasing
26.7.1989	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.31	1.32-1.33 increasing	5.1	0.35-0.36 increasing
1.10.-4.10.1989	-0.61	89-96 decreasing	1.87-1.94 decreasing	4.45-6.65 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
2.11.1989	weaker than +9.50	<1	1.19-1.20 decreasing	0.78-0.79 increasing	5.6	0.42
2.1.1990	-0.86	98-100 decreasing	1.84-1.85 decreasing	2.18-2.68 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.30-0.31 decreasing
16.2.1990	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.02	1.08	6.6	0.47
3.4.-4.4.1990	-1.00	98-100 increasing	1.73-1.74 increasing	1.86-2.82 decreasing	3.8-3.9 decreasing	0.30-0.31 increasing
5.6.-6.6.1990	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.97-0.98 increasing	2.15-2.16 decreasing	6.8-6.9 decreasing	0.40-0.41 decreasing
4.7.-5.7.1990	-0.89	88-91	1.61-1.63	7.91-8.33	4.1-4.2	0.31-0.32

1990		increasing	increasing	decreasing	decreasing	increasing
16.9.1990	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.09-1.10	0.62-0.63	6.1-6.2	0.33
5.10.-8.10.1990	-0.44	72-81 increasing	1.56-1.64 increasing	11.09-12.16 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.36 increasing
8.11.-15.11.1990	+0.16	93-98 decreasing	1.87-1.93 decreasing	5.49-8.80 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
28.11.-30.11.1990	+0.06	70-76 decreasing	1.63-1.68 decreasing	13.60-13.95 increasing	4.0-4.1 increasing	0.40-0.42 decreasing
22.12.1990	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.23	0.64-0.65 increasing	5.4	0.31
11.1.-15.1.1991	+0.15	66-76 increasing	1.65-1.75 increasing	13.03-13.72 decreasing	3.8-4.1 decreasing	0.39-0.42 increasing
30.1.-4.2.1991	+0.28	95-98 increasing	1.99-2.04 increasing	4.95-6.99 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
4.3.-7.3.1991	-0.17	75-83 decreasing	1.77-1.84 decreasing	9.84-10.70 increasing	3.6-3.8 increasing	0.35-0.37 decreasing
27.3.1991	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31-1.32 decreasing	1.23-1.24 increasing	5.1	0.32-0.33 increasing
6.6.-8.6.1991	-0.41	83-90 decreasing	1.86-1.93 decreasing	6.95-8.30 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.34 decreasing
1.7.1991	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.30	1.29-1.30 increasing	5.1	0.37
5.9.-8.9.1991	-0.66	91-97 decreasing	1.87-1.93 decreasing	4.01-6.08 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
9.10.-10.10.1991	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.16	0.54-0.55 increasing	5.8	0.43
6.12.-9.12.1991	-0.89	98-100 decreasing	1.81-1.84 decreasing	0.38-3.00 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.30-0.31 decreasing

Made with STELLARIUM and PLANETARIUM.